

Of 165 new rice varieties released to farmers in Asia over a 5-year period, 64% either were progeny of IRRI rices or were IRRI varieties or experimental lines. Twenty-two percent of the rices were developed at IRRI and 42% were progeny of local crosses involving an IRRI parent. One hundred and sixty-five newest varieties released from 1970 to 1975 at 29 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 10 Asian nations, 1975.

Forty-two percent of the varieties were progeny of crosses involving an IRRI variety or line as a parent. (Of the 129 locally developed varieties, 54% were IRRI progeny.) A total of 64% of the sample of 165 newest varieties in 10 countries were either progeny of IRRI rices or had been developed at IRRI. ❧

Advanced breeding lines in 10 Asian nations

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Because most of the future rice varieties released for farmer use in Asia will come from advanced yield trials, IRRI collected information on the types of plant materials included in the trials. Rice breeders were surveyed at 28 research centers in 10 countries in mid-1975. The research project was partially funded by a research grant from The Rockefeller Foundation.

It was found that 4,163 advanced breeding lines were being tested in 29 yield trials at the 28 stations. The mean number was 144 lines/trial, with a range of from 12 to 630 lines/trial.

For most of the trials, the responsible breeder indicated how many of the advanced lines were developed at that

Data were collected on 4,021 breeding lines of rice in 27 advanced yield trials in Asia. *a*. Fifty-nine percent of the advanced lines originated from crosses made at the local research centers; 41% originated from crosses made outside of the local centers. *b*. Of 1,406 introduced lines in 17 trials, 60% came from other research centers in the same country and 39%, from IRRI. From a survey of advanced experimental lines of rice in 9 Asian nations, 1975.

station and how many came from outside sources (other breeding centers in that country, other countries, or IRRI). These data were collected on 4,021 breeding lines in 27 advanced yield trials in 9 countries.

Fifty-nine percent of the genetic material (2363 lines) originated from local crosses made at the breeders' stations; 41% (1658 lines) originated outside of the stations (see figure, *a*).

Next, the origin was determined of the introduced lines (the advanced lines that did not come from local crosses). Data were obtained for 1,406 of the introduced breeding lines in 17 advanced yield trials in 8 countries.

Sixty percent of the introduced genetic material (842 lines) came from crosses made at other research centers within the same country as the surveyed experiment station; 39% (543 lines) came from IRRI; and about 1% (21 lines) came from breeding programs in other Asian nations (see figure, *b*).

To further measure the diversity of the genetic background of improved local lines, breeders at 20 research centers in 8 countries were asked to indicate the number of crosses from which they selected 3,791 locally developed lines in 22 advanced trials. The lines had been selected from 443 crosses – an average of 8.6 advanced lines/cross. ❧

Effect of seedling on the growth and yield of rice varieties

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Rice varieties Bala, Saket 1, and Ratna were transplanted at 24, 29, 34, 44, and 49 days to study the growth behavior and extent of yield reduction when transplanting is delayed. The experiment was conducted at Allahabad Agricultural

Institute during the 1976 kharif season using a split-plot design with four replications. Varieties were in main plots and seedlings of different ages were in subplots.

When older seedlings of the short-duration variety Bala were transplanted, tiller number and yield were consistently reduced. Saket 1 and Ratna (medium- and long-duration rices) gave higher values when planted at 29 days of age than when planted at any other age (see table). The short-duration variety may be transplanted until the age of 34 days,

Yield components of three rice varieties transplanted at different seedling ages. Allahabad Agricultural Institute, India.

Seedling age (days)	Effective tillers (no./hill) ^a			Grains (panicle/no.)			1,000-grain wt (g)			Yield (t/ha)		
	Bala	Saket 1	Ratna	Bala	Saket 1	Ratna	Bala	Saket 1	Ratna	Bala	Saket 1	Ratna
24	12.5	9.7	13.7	122	140	119	18.5	19.8	19.4	2.6	3.2	3.1
29	10.2	11.1	13.8	116	152	124	18.5	19.7	19.5	2.6	3.6	3.8
34	9.9	10.4	13.1	111	135	118	17.9	19.6	19.1	2.4	3.0	2.9
39	8.6	9.7	12.3	100	132	114	17.7	19.3	19.1	1.3	2.9	2.8
44	7.3	9.5	10.4	93	132	107	17.3	19.2	18.8	1.0	2.1	2.0
49	5.2	7.4	8.7	89	123	105	17.3	18.2	18.3	1.0	1.6	1.0

^aTwo seedlings planted per hill at 20 × 20 cm.

while the medium- and long-duration varieties may be transplanted until 39 days for profitable rice production.

The experiment is being repeated in 1977 to better quantify the growth and yield performance of short-, medium-,

and long-duration rice varieties under Indian conditions. ❧

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Grain quality

The mechanism of gibberellic-acid action on rice

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Treating rice with gibberellic acid (GA) produces long and thin stems and causes lodging. Silica content in the cell walls of stems of treated plants is equal to that of control plants. GA inhibits tillering and activates ramification. Spikelet sterility becomes high and panicle weight becomes low.

GA reduces the content of riboflavin and free thiamine in leaves, but increases the content of total thiamine and cocarboxylase. It competitively inhibits flavin oxydases and increases indoleacetic acid (IAA) content. In the apexes of plants treated with GA, the ratio of RNA to DNA increases but the total protein content does not. The number of electrophoretical fractions of acid albumins decreases.

GA increases the variability of free amino acids set, but reduces their total content in primordial panicles of rice.

The content of free proline is reduced rather sharply, while that of histones is increased. The stream of information from nucleus to cytoplasm grows narrow with GA. GA is likely to affect the information transfer system.

Hence, this is the mechanism of GA action: proline (initiator of flowering) content is reduced, but the content of both histones (repressors of the generative group of genes) and growth stimulators (IAA) is increased. ❧

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

New sources of resistance to bacterial leaf streak of rice

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Bacterial leaf streak of rice, caused by *Xanthomonas translucens*, f. sp. *oryzicola*, is becoming a more important disease with intensive cultivation of newly introduced high yielding varieties. Both the early- and late-duration rices have been observed to become susceptible under conditions of high humidity, cloudiness, and drizzles. Thus the disease can become severe in high-rainfall areas of eastern and northeastern India. At the Central Rice Research Institute (CRR I), a severe incidence of the disease appeared on the variety Pankaj during kharif 1972. Several fixed cultivars of upland rice

grown during kharif 1977 were also severely affected.

Out of 50 artificially inoculated cultivars from the Assam Rice Collections, ARC 13899 and ARC 13962 were found resistant. Among the popular varieties tested, NC 1281 was highly resistant. It is being extensively used at CRR I to develop high yielding varieties that are sensitive to photoperiod. It has good tolerance to gall midge and is considered to have high photosynthetic ability under low light intensity. Several F₄ progeny from the cross NC 1281/ Pankaj were artificially inoculated during kharif 1977. The progeny clearly segregated for susceptibility or resistance to bacterial leaf streak. That shows that the inheritance may be simple and it may not be difficult to fix resistant lines.